

Development of new cloud point extraction procedure using mixed micelles of TX-114 and DOSS for the determination of azocarmine G

Sk. Ameer Khan^a, P. Shyamala^{*a}, K. Ravi Kumar^a and D. Suneetha^b

^aDepartment of Physical and Nuclear Chemistry & Chemical Oceanography, School of Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail: shyamalapulipaka06@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Government Degree College, Yeleswaram-533 429, East Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 09 May 2018, revised 29 May 2018, accepted 31 May 2018

A new cloud point extraction (CPE) procedure with spectrophotometry for the preconcentration and extraction of azocarmine G (ACG) has been developed using mixed micelles of Triton X-114 (TX-114) and Docusate sodium salt (DOSS) at a pH of 4.6. In this method the dye azocarmine G was extracted into the surfactant rich phase of mixed micelles of TX-114 and DOSS by heating the sample at 70°C for 20 min. Various parameters effecting the extraction of dye like pH, concentration of TX-114, concentration of DOSS, equilibrium temperature and equilibrium time were optimized. Under optimum conditions the linear range of azocarmine G was found to be 0.0–23.18 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The corresponding detection limit was found to be 0.0041 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. The proposed method has been successfully applied to the extraction of azocarmine G in tap water and sea water and recoveries were found to be in the range of 89.91–106.9%.

Keywords: Cloud point extraction, mixed micelles, spectrophotometry, TX-114, DOSS.

Introduction

Azocarmine G (ACG) (Fig. 1) is a common biological stain used to determine proteins¹, DNA² and light neurons³. It is also used as food colorant to make foodstuffs visually attractive⁴. These azodyes can decompose to produce over 20 kinds of carcinogenic aromatic amines, which cause lesions and induce cancer after activation to change the DNA structure of the human body⁵. There is a need for the determination of these dyes since they are common effluents from textile, chemical and printing industries which affect the quality

Fig. 1. Structure of azocarmine G.

of drinking water^{6–9}.

Many analytical techniques like TLC (Thin layer chromatography)^{10,11}, HPLC (High performance liquid chromatography)^{12,13}, voltammetry¹⁴ have been developed for the extraction and preconcentration of dyes. However these methods involve time consuming sample pretreatments. Cloud point extraction (CPE) is an alternative effective preconcentration method which is based on the clouding behaviour of micellar solutions. In this method, the aqueous solution of surfactants are heated and at a certain temperature they become turbid and separate into two distinct phases, aqueous phase and surfactant rich phase. The temperature is called cloud point temperature and metal ions can be extracted into the surfactant rich phase. The method has several advantages like low cost, simplicity, lower toxicity to environment which makes it a green method than solvent extraction procedures. It also has a high capacity to concentrate a wide variety of analytes with high efficiency^{15,16}.

In the CPE technique, the most common surfactant used is of non-ionic type like Triton X-114 (polyoxyethylene-7.5-

octylphenoxy ether), Triton X-100 (polyoxyethylene-9.5-octylphenoxy ether) and PONPE (polynonylphenyl ether) since their cloud point temperatures are close to room temperature. The use of cationic or anionic surfactant in combination with a non-ionic surfactant has been reported with an increase in the extraction efficiency of compounds^{17,18}. Moreover, the mixture of surfactants makes the method convenient to use. The cloud point temperature of TX-114 is around 25°C and that of DOSS (Bis(2-ethylhexyl) sulfosuccinate sodium salt) is around 100°C. The use of DOSS alone requires high temperature around 100°C while the mixture of surfactants reduces the temperature to 50°C, which is convenient for extraction procedure.

In the present work, a cloud point extraction (CPE) procedure based on mixed micelles of Triton X-114 (TX-114) and Docusate sodium salt (DOSS) for the determination of

azocarmine G has been developed. The results are reported.

Results and discussion

The azocarmine G dye was extracted into mixed micelles of TX-114 and DOSS in the presence of sodium sulphate. For maximum extraction efficiency, the parameters affecting the cloud point extraction were optimized. The optimum conditions are discussed below.

Optimization of pH:

To maintain pH in the range from 1 to 8, different buffers with combinations of KCl/HCl¹⁹, CH₃COONa/CH₃COOH and NaH₂PO₄/Na₂HPO₄ were used. Maximum recovery was observed for azocarmine G with acetate buffer (CH₃COONa/CH₃COOH) at a pH of 4.6. Therefore, pH 4.6 was chosen for the extraction of azocarmine G dye in subsequent experiments (Fig. 2(a)).

Fig. 2. (a) Effect of pH on the recovery of the azocarmine G (Experimental conditions: 1.2% w/v of TX-114; 0.6% w/v of DOSS; 2.4% w/v of Na₂SO₄; equilibration temperature 70°C; equilibration time 20 min). (b) Effect of concentration of TX-114 on the recovery of the azocarmine G (Experimental conditions: pH 4.6; 0.6% w/v of DOSS; 2.4% w/v of Na₂SO₄; equilibration temperature 70°C; equilibration time 20 min). (c) Effect of concentration of DOSS on the recovery of the azocarmine G (Experimental conditions: pH 4.6; 1.2% w/v of TX-114; 2.4% w/v of Na₂SO₄; equilibration temperature 70°C; equilibration time 20 min). (d) Effect of concentration of Na₂SO₄ on the recovery of the azocarmine G (Experimental conditions: pH 4.6; 1.2% w/v of TX-114; 0.6% w/v of DOSS; equilibration temperature 70°C; equilibration time 20 min).

Optimization of concentration of surfactants (TX-114 and DOSS):

The recovery of ACG dye was studied in the concentration range of TX-114 from 0.2% w/v to 3% w/v. The recovery of ACG increased up to 1.2% w/v of TX-114 and then decreased. Thus, the optimum concentration of TX-114 was 1.2% w/v for ACG (Fig. 2(b)).

To increase the extraction efficiency of dye the anionic surfactant, DOSS has been used along with TX-114. The concentration of TX-114 was fixed at 1.2% w/v and DOSS was optimized in the range 0.1% w/v to 1.0% w/v. The recovery increases up to 0.6% w/v of DOSS and then decreases. Therefore the optimum concentration of DOSS is 0.6% w/v (Fig. 2(c)).

Optimization of concentration of Na₂SO₄:

To facilitate the separation of the two phases, a salt is added so that the density of the aqueous phase increases. The addition of Na₂SO₄ to the mixture of TX-114 and DOSS also reduces the cloud point temperature of the system. The recovery of dye increased with increase in the Na₂SO₄ concentration until 2.4% w/v and then the recovery decreased. The optimum concentration of Na₂SO₄ was found to be 2.4% w/v for ACG dye (Fig. 2(d)).

Optimization of equilibration temperature and time:

The phase separation for the mixed micelles of TX-114 and DOSS was not observed below 50°C and the recoveries increased with increase in temperature up to 70°C for ACG dye and then decreased. In the study of equilibration time, the recoveries increased up to 20 min and then decreased. Hence, the optimum equilibration temperature and time were found to be 70°C for ACG dye and 20 min, respectively.

Analytical characteristics of the method:

The analytical characteristics of the proposed method were evaluated under the optimized conditions. Calibration graph was drawn for ACG dye under the optimum conditions, from which the observed linearity range for ACG was found to be 0.0–23.18 µg mL⁻¹. The calibration equation obtained was $A = 0.040 C_{ACG} + 0.010$ with correlation coefficient of 0.998. The detection limit was found to be 0.0041 µg mL⁻¹. The preconcentration factor of the method was 20 and the extraction efficiency of the method was 94.4%.

Applications:

The proposed mixed micellar cloud point extraction method was successfully applied for the extraction of ACG dye in tap and sea water samples. The spike recoveries were found to be in the range from 89.91–106.9%. The results are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of azocarmine G in the real samples and their spike recoveries in the present proposed method

Samples	Spiked (µg mL ⁻¹)	Detected (µg mL ⁻¹)	Recovery (%)
Tap water	–	ND ^a	–
	5.79	6.19	106.9
	11.59	11.52	99.41
Sea water	–	ND ^a	–
	5.79	5.20	89.91
	11.59	12.21	105.4

^aNot Detected.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions:

All reagents used were of analytical grade and double distilled water was used throughout. Stock solution of 10% w/v TX-114 (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was prepared by dissolving 10 g of the compound in double distilled water and 10% w/v DOSS (Docusate sodium salt, Fluka, USA) was prepared by dissolving 10 g of DOSS in methanol. Stock solution of azocarmine G (1×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving 0.0579 g of azocarmine G in 100 mL of double distilled water. Stock solution of sodium sulphate 30% w/v was prepared by dissolving 30 g of the salt in 100 mL of double distilled water. For HCl/KCl buffer, 1 mol L⁻¹ KCl was prepared by dissolving 7.455 g of KCl in 100 mL of double distilled water. 1 mol L⁻¹ HCl was prepared by dissolving 9 mL of HCl in 100 mL of double distilled water and standardized against standard NaOH solution. For acetate buffer 1 mol L⁻¹ CH₃COONa was prepared by dissolving 8.203 g of CH₃COONa in 100 mL of double distilled water. 1 mol L⁻¹ CH₃COOH was prepared by dissolving 5.8 mL of CH₃COOH in 100 mL of double distilled water and standardized against standard NaOH solution. For phosphate buffer 1 mol L⁻¹ NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O was prepared by dissolving 15.6 g of NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O in 100 mL of double distilled water. 1 mol L⁻¹ Na₂HPO₄ was prepared by dissolving 14.2 g of Na₂HPO₄ in 100 mL of double distilled water.

CPE procedure: Aliquot solutions containing azocarmine G solution at a pH of 4.6 with concentrations varying from 0.0 to 23.8 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, 1.2 mL of 10% w/v TX-114, 0.6 mL of 10% w/v DOSS and 0.8 mL of 30% w/v Na_2SO_4 were taken in a centrifuge tube and diluted to 10 mL with double distilled water. The solution was heated to 70°C in a thermostat for 20 min, which resulted into two phases. Subsequently, complete phase separation was obtained through centrifugation and cooling for 15 min in an ice bath, then the supernatant aqueous phase was decanted. The surfactant rich phase was dissolved in 20% methanol to decrease the viscosity and homogenized surfactant rich phase was analyzed spectrophotometrically.

Equipment:

A double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV-1800, Shimadzu, Japan) with an accuracy of 0.001 nm was used for measuring for the absorbance and recording the spectra. The absorbance of azocarmine G in aqueous solution showed a maximum absorbance band at 528 nm and all the measurements were carried out at this wavelength.

A Systronics digital pH meter 335 was used for pH measurements.

A Remi R-24 centrifuge machine was used for centrifugation of samples.

Conclusions

Mixed micelles of TX-114 (1.2% w/v) and DOSS (0.6% w/v) based on cloud point extraction procedure were used for the determination and extraction of azocarmine G. The developed method was then applied to real water samples. The proposed cloud point extraction method proved to be sensitive, selective, low cost and accurate, which allows the determination of azocarmine G at mg mL^{-1} level.

Acknowledgement

The authors (PS and KRK) are grateful to the Department of Science and Technology (DST-SERB), India, for financial support under the major research project SB/S1/IC-

35/2013. One of the authors SAK is also grateful to the University Grants Commission, India, for financial support under JRF scheme (Ref. No. 3009118875).

References

1. W. Lin-lin, W. Jun-fang, Z. Yuan, D. Zhong-tao and C. Qiu'e, *J. Yunnan Univ. Nat. Sci.*, 2008, **30**, 83.
2. C. Zhan-guang, R. Feng-lian, S. Shi-hui, L. Xu-hong, D. Wei-feng and L. Jin-bin, *J. Cent. South Univ. Technol.*, 2005, **12**, 688.
3. T. Murakami, T. Murakami, N. Mahmut, S. Hitomi and A. Ohtsuka, *Arch. Histol. Cytol.*, 1997, **60**, 265.
4. J. Luan, Y. Shen, S. Wang and N. Guo, *Polymers*, 2017, **9**, 69.
5. S. Bonan, G. Fedrizzi, S. Menotta and C. Elisabetta, *Dyes Pigm.*, 2013, **99**, 36.
6. S. D. Dalt, A. K. Alves and C. P. Bergmann, *Mater. Res. Bull.*, 2013, **48**, 1845.
7. A. K. Sinha, M. Pradhan, S. Sarkar and T. Pal, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2013, **47**, 2339.
8. T. M. Breault and B. M. Bartlett, *J. Phys. Chem. (C)*, 2013, **117**, 8611.
9. X. Zhou, Q. Xu, W. Lei, T. Zhang, X. Qi, G. Liu, K. Deng and J. Yu, *Small*, 2014, **10**, 674.
10. F. Soponar, A. Cătălin Moț and C. Sârbu, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2008, **1188**, 295.
11. K. Harada, K. Masuda and M. Suzuki, *Biol. Mass Spectrom.*, 1991, **20**, 522.
12. M. Aparecido, G. Trindade, M. V. B. Zanoni and F. Matysik, *Fuel*, 2010, **89**, 2463.
13. M. Šuleková, A. Hudák and M. Smrèová, *Molecules*, 2016, **21**, 1368.
14. A. H. Alghamdi, H. M. Alshammery, M. A. Abdalla and A. F. Alghamdi, *J. AOAC Int.*, 2009, **92**, 1454.
15. F. H. Quina and W. L. Hinze, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 1999, **38**, 4150.
16. A. Shokrollahi and F. D. Kashkoli, *Chin. Chem. Lett.*, 2016, **27**, 659.
17. N. N. Meeravali and S. J. Jiang, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2008, **23**, 1365.
18. Z. Xiaohong, Z. Xiashi and B. Wang, *J. Anal. At. Spectrom.*, 2006, **21**, 69.
19. N. T. Hwisa, S. K. Adiki, P. Katakam and B. R. Chandu, *J. Appl. Pharm. Sci.*, 2013, **3(6)**, 106.